

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D10.1
Project Website

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871542

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	ICT-871542
Starting Date	1 st January, 2020
Duration	48 months
Call Identifier	H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic	ICT-09-2019-2020 (B) (IA)
Project Website	http://www.piloting-project.eu
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Document Information

Due date: 31/03/2020	Submission date: 21/03/2020
Data of request for revision: 29/11/2021	Revision Submission date: 08/02/2022
Lead beneficiary: CATEC	Version: 2.0
Work Package	10- Exploitation, Communication and Dissemination
Deliverable Title	Project Website
Main Editor(s)	CATEC
Contributor(s)	CATEC
Reviewer (s)	USE

Document Classification					
Status	F	Nature	DEC	Dissemination level	PU
Draft: D Final: F		R = Report P = Prototype D = Demonstrator O = Other DEC: Websites, press & media actions, videos, etc.		PU = Public PP = Restricted to other programme participants* RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium * *including the Commission Services	

Revision history			
Version	Issue Date	Status	Autor(s)
0.8	28.01.2020	First Draft	CATEC
0.9	04.02.2020	Review process	USE
1.0	21.03.2020	Final version	CATEC

Contents

1. INTRODUCTION.....	5
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	5
1.2 Scope of the document.....	5
1.3 Structure of the document.....	5
2. WEBSITE CONTENT.....	5
2.1 Website structure.....	5
2.2 Website Home tab.....	6
2.3 Project Overview tab.....	8
2.4 Consortium tab.....	15
2.5 News tab.....	17
2.6 Public Material tab.....	18
3. DOCUMENT REPOSITORY.....	19
3.1 Repository Structure.....	20
3.1.1 To-dos.....	20
3.1.2 Docs&Files.....	21
3.1.3 Schedule.....	22
3.1.4 Message board.....	23
4. CONCLUSIONS.....	24

List of Figures

Figure 1. PILOTING website structure.	6
Figure 2. “Home” tab.....	8
Figure 3. “Project Overview” content	8
Figure 4. “Project Overview” →”About project”	9
Figure 5. “Project Overview” →”Challenges”	10
Figure 6. “Project Overview” →”Objectives”	11
Figure 7. “Project Overview” →”PILOTING Uses Cases”.....	14
Figure 8. “Project Overview” →”Cooperation”.....	15
Figure 9. “Consortium” tab	16
Figure 10. “Project Overview” →”FADA-CATEC” tab	17
Figure 11. “News” tab	18
Figure 12. “Public material” →” Publications and datasets” tab	19
Figure 13. “Multimedia” tab.....	19
Figure 14. PILOTING repository initial screen.	20
Figure 15. PILOTING repository “To-dos” section.....	21
Figure 16. PILOTING repository “Docs&Files” section	22
Figure 17. PILOTING repository “Schedule” section.....	23
Figure 18. PILOTING repository “Message board” section	23

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the document

The deliverable D10.1 Project website is produced within Work package 10 (Exploitation, communication and dissemination) of the PILOTING project, under the Task 10.3 (Dissemination, communication and engaging the I&M community), in order to support dissemination activities.

The purpose of this document is to attest the launching of the PILOTING Project Website on the scheduled date.

1.2 Scope of the document

This document gives an overview of the PILOTING website which is available at <https://piloting-project.eu/> and provides the necessary functions to act as a dissemination tool and information resource of the project. The website will be used by the project consortium as well as external stakeholders to disseminate the main project research progress, findings, outputs and activities.

The PILOTING website contains general information about the project, including the project's objectives, methodology, main outcomes, consortium presentation, project news, related links (including the social media channels), etc. It also will give access to the public deliverables and publications generated within the project.

The project website has been launched in January 2020, and it will be updated and improved in a fully operative format throughout the project lifetime.

1.3 Structure of the document

In the next sections, the content of PILOTING public website and repository are presented.

2. WEBSITE CONTENT

2.1 Website structure

The structure of the PILOTING website reflects the main areas of the project that need to be communicated to the wide public and keep the project visible. All the content has been carefully selected basing on the initial information on the project expressed in the project proposal.

The webpage has been structured in the sections shown in Figure 1. Each section can be accessed by an item in a lateral menu.

Figure 1. PILOTING website structure.

2.2 Website Home tab

The “Home” tab of PILOTING website supposes the first overview of the project for the website users. This tab has the following functions:

- Present the purpose and the scope of PILOTING project.
- Present the main challenges of PILOTING project.
- Presentation of PILOTING Uses cases.
- Inform about the latest PILOTING news, like main project outcomes, latest developments, presentations at relevant events, workshops organized within the project, newsletters, , etc.
- Present the project consortium including partner’s logos and respective links.
- Provide the multimedia content developed within the project.
- Provide the links to LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube.
- Give contact information.

The PILOTING website “Home” tab is presented in the Figure 2 below.

HOME

PROJECT OVERVIEW ▾

CONSORTIUM ▾

NEWS

PUBLIC MATERIAL ▾

PILOTING PROPOSES

The adaptation, integration, and demonstration of robotic solutions, in an integrated platform, which will be tested and evaluated in three large-scale pilots: refineries, bridges/viaducts and tunnels with the involvement of all the actors that conform the full value chain.

If you are interested in PILOTING project, please send an email to piloting-project@catec.aero to become a member PILOTING User Group

ABOUT THE PROJECT

LATEST NEWS

Videopresentation of PILOTING from CATEC

[Read More](#)

The H2020 PILOTING project starts with an excellent kick-off meeting in Seville

[Read More](#)

NEWS

CHALLENGES

The main focus of PILOTING project is to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities in order to keep the necessary safety levels in aging infrastructures. To achieve this increment, the inspection & maintenance industry is facing the following major challenges.

HALLENGES

CHALLENGES 1
Reduction of current inspection costs and outage time.

CHALLENGES 2
Production and access to reliable inspection data.

CHALLENGES 3
Increase of Personnel safety.

Figure 2. “Home” tab

2.3 Project Overview tab

This tab includes a general summary of the project concept, the challenges of the Inspection & Maintenance industry that will be faced by PILOTING project, the objectives pursue to overcome the challenges, the pilot uses cases defined within the project as well as the main advances in this sense and, finally, presentation of other European initiatives focused on developing I&M robotic solutions, with which PILOTING collaborates (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. “Project Overview” content

The PILOTING website “Project Overview” tab is presented from Figure 4 to Figure 8.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Current European refineries and civil Infrastructures, like tunnels and bridges, are ageing, and therefore gradually become deteriorated, especially taking into consideration the current and future economic situation in Europe where large Investments in renewing Infrastructures are not foreseen.

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CHALLENGES

The PILOTING Integrated platform will: demonstrate the application of robotics at scale in the domain of Inspection and Maintenance (I&M), reduce end-user commercial risks on the deployment of robotics in the sector, demonstrate capabilities and improve understanding of robotics uptake value, develop and support the related ecosystem around the piloting I&M operations, as well as, contribute to industrial standards in robotics for I&M.

PILOTING PROPOSES

Then, it is paramount important to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities in order to keep the necessary safety levels in these ageing infrastructures. To overcome this important challenge, PILOTING proposes the adaptation, integration, and demonstration of robotic solutions, in an integrated platform, which will be tested and evaluated in three large-scale pilots: refineries (Oil&Gas sector), bridges/viaducts and tunnels (Civil/Transport Infrastructure sector) with the involvement of all the actors that conform the full value chain.

Figure 4. “Project Overview” →”About project”

CHALLENGES

The main focus of PILOTING project is to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities in order to keep the necessary safety levels in ageing infrastructures. To achieve this increment, the Inspection & Maintenance Industry is facing the following major challenges:

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OBJECTIVES

CHALLENGES 1

Current inspection methodologies are based on manual inspection procedures which are low-speed and require, most of the times, infrastructures' shut-down. The use of robotic technologies in PILOTING will importantly decrease cost and time of inspection and maintenance operations since it avoids unnecessary disruption and downtime, and facilitates enormously the access to high and/or dangerous locations.

CHALLENGES 2

Nowadays inspection authorities and personnel lack in using repeatable and reproducible inspection data, often found deficient in quality measurements (highly dependent on the skill and experience of the inspector). Errors in or limited quality of inspection measurement data can have important consequences that may lead to damages to the infrastructure or health risks to the public or infrastructure personnel. PILOTING will provide high precision measurement data (gathered by the robotic vehicles) structured and presented in a seamless but trustworthy approach towards the inspection personnel and maintenance teams following international and well-established reporting approaches.

CHALLENGES 3

Personnel access and probability of accidental falls and injuries represent the vastly predominant cost of the inspection. Having personnel working on elevated structures and dangerous locations requires planning, presence of support personnel, which implicitly implies slow progress in the measurement operations. PILOTING will contribute to increase personnel safety through advanced and automated robotic systems that will decrease drastically the exposure of operators to dangerous situations.

Figure 5. “Project Overview” →”Challenges”

OBJECTIVES

In order to overcome the Identified challenges, PILOTING has established the following objectives

If you are interested in PILOTING project, please send an email to piloting-project@catec.aero to become a member PILOTING User Group

CONSORTIUM

OBJECTIVES 1

Adapt advanced robotics supported by artificial intelligence technologies to the end-users needs and increase their technological readiness levels for the three considered scenarios.

Adapt advanced robotics supported by artificial intelligence technologies to the end-users needs and increase their technological readiness levels for the three considered scenarios.

OBJECTIVES 2

Design and develop the PILOTING I&M open and scalable platform.

PILOTING I&M platform will be designed following a scalable architecture using open interfaces. The PILOTING architecture and interfaces will be promoted during the project as a future industrial standard that will facilitate the integration of robotic solutions into new business cases related to inspection and maintenance.

OBJECTIVES 3

Integrate the full value chain to demonstrate benefits of the PILOTING technological developments through large-scale pilots in real conditions and infrastructures.

These pilots will not only demonstrate the developed technologies, but it will also involve the full value chain (from technological providers, to inspection service providers and asset owners) ensuring the future industrial application and exploitation of PILOTING technological developments.

OBJECTIVES 4

Overcome current barriers in inspection and maintenance robotics.

Previous robotics I&M projects have been mainly focused on pure technological development. While PILOTING project will concentrate on fulfilling realistic end-users requirements and operational restrictions where congested structures, air turbulence, lack of line-of-sight navigation, weather conditions among others need consideration.

OBJECTIVES 5

Support to the promotion of European robotic solutions within the inspection and maintenance industry.

This objective will involve the dissemination of best practices, the development of business models that validate the added value of robotic technologies, and the impact of ethical, societal, privacy and cybersecurity aspects on the use of robotics technologies in inspections and maintenance operations. Furthermore, it will be promoted the connections of applied robotic technologies with IoT (Internet of Things) and 5G-related technologies.

Figure 6. “Project Overview” →”Objectives”

PILOTING USES CASES

REFINERIES BRIDGES/VIADUCTS TUNNELS

If you are interested in PILOTING project, please send an email to piloting-project@catec.aero to become a member PILOTING User Group

COOPERATION

REFINERIES

REFINERY GROUND MONITORING

Currently, refineries require the involvement of thousands of workers on-site in a single plant. Most of them are exposed to dangerous situations and extreme conditions in isolated sites. Thus, there is a clear drive for the Oil and Gas industry in reducing as much as possible the presence of operators in a refinery facility. Operations like monitoring and inspection routines require the presence of personnel for tasks like for example analogy sensor readings. The present use case addresses the use of robotic technologies to automatize routinely inspection tasks that currently are carried out by the operators surveying the plant on foot.

REFINERY VESSELS INSPECTION

Inspections from the interior of vessels are characterized by working in enclosed spaces. The associated safety risks to service personnel are a major factor for refinery owners. PILOTING proposes using robotic crawlers to carry out the inspection tasks minimizing the preparation time before entering the vessel and avoiding or significantly reducing the time a human must spend in the confined space. Equipment required for human entry and work, such as scaffolding and ventilation, can be foregone as well, further reducing costs and job duration. Robotic systems also offer an opportunity to gather inspection data that is more comprehensive, reliable and repeatable.

REFINERY PIPES INSPECTION

Inspection of process pipes using non-destructive testing (NDT) methods is crucial for the oil and gas industry. A typical plant may contain several kilometers of pipework, and the identification of features such as valves, bends, tee joints, and welds can be difficult. Henceforth, the development and consolidation of a high TRL robotic solution for NDT pipes inspection is a priority for the end-user. The experience gained from previous project triggers the use a hybrid robot for this type of inspection. Thus, the so-called Hybrid Mobile Robot (HMR) is composed of an aerial platform and a satellite robot. The aerial platform houses the satellite, which is in charge of the inspection itself.

REFINERY LARGE STRUCTURES INSPECTION

Large structures are frequent all over an Oil & Gas refinery. Their manual inspection is tedious, as well as slow since it is currently done with operators hanged from the top of the structure. They have to descend over the structure, take the measurement and move, usually with significant risks and time, to the next point. Hence, the inspection of these kinds of infrastructures with a UAV can be potentially exploited by the industry. The current use case aims to perform non-destructive testing (NDT) inspections by mean of an aerial robot, which will carry the sensors for the inspection.

BRIDGES / VIADUCTS

VIADUCT - SURVEYING TARGETS INSTALLATION FOR GEOMETRICAL PRECISE MEASUREMENTS

In order to measure the impact of visual defects on the structure from an image is to be able to calculate some of its properties. For example, if the defect is a crack, we can measure its length, width, orientation and depth. Following this example, we can easily measure the length and orientation and we definitely can't measure the depth with an image. The width though, can be too small to measure it with enough accuracy just with the picture. That is why we need to use small surveying passive targets with a millimetric or sub-millimetric pattern, which can be used as a reference to improve the accuracy of the measurement. Moreover, those passive devices can also include a reflective part which can be also used for precise geometrical measurements by advanced tools like a total station. Therefore, it has been considered the installation of surveying targets.

VIADUCT - SENSOR INSTALLATION

There are cases where it is no possible to detect defects through the visual inspection, on the viaduct. However, there are devices that can help to detect different types of non-visible defects. For instance, a sensor box with sensors like accelerometers or IMUs can monitor the viaduct structure. These boxes should be placed on the right location to work, and that location happens to be difficult to access most of the times (e.g. above the pillars). An aerial robot with manipulation capabilities could help installing these devices. On the one hand, this robot will be able to place a metric sticker on the pillars. On the other hand, this robot will also be able to carry the sensor box and place it on top of the pillar.

VIADUCT BEARINGS INSPECTION

Bearings are a critical part of a viaduct structure. They support the deck over the pillars. Thus, it is very relevant to periodically inspect them looking for defects which could indicate the deterioration of the material and the loss of the bearing performance. The main issue is that bearings are highly inaccessible, just between the deck and the top of the pillars. A small aerial robot, with the ability to attach to the bottom of the viaduct's deck and move without losing contact with it, would allow getting close to the bearings. In addition, sticking to the deck makes the aerial robot more stable and then it will be able to take better high-quality images of the bearings from all the angles.

VIADUCT VISUAL INSPECTION

A first step to be performed in such a large structure as a viaduct is to carry out a general visual inspection. Due to the dimensions of this type of infrastructures, the detection of defects is slow, and it frequently derives in an inherent danger for the operator. Hence, firstly general visual inspection will be carried out with a UAV along the viaduct. This first inspection will aim to detect as many defects as possible. Once this general inspection has been conducted, the main defects to be monitored will be selected. After that, and once the devices installation has been performed, the UAV will come back to those defects that have been prepared for a more detailed inspection.

TUNNELS

TUNNEL LOCAL INSPECTION

This use case is a more thorough inspection of the tunnel, stopping to get every possible detail of the previously detected defects or even detecting new ones. In order to achieve this level of detail, the system consists of two robots, one ground robot and one aerial robot. The ground robot has several advantages like the autonomy, the stability and the payload capacity. At the general tunnel inspection, this robot is in charge of inspecting all the details of the defects it could. However, tunnels are big, and there might be parts of it that are too far from the ground robot to get the required accuracy in some measurements. The aerial robot can get closer to those defects and then take the detailed measurements, while the ground robot provides the precise localization of the robotic system along system.

TUNNEL GENERAL INSPECTION

The objective of the tunnel general inspection use case is to obtain an overview of the tunnel condition as well as the location of possible issues/faults to be more closely inspected during the more detailed local inspection. The inspection mission will be carried out using a robotic cart fitted with various sensors to allow safe and autonomous navigation in tunnel environments. The information collected will be used to localize and visualize detected issues/faults within the tunnel, giving operators an improved situational understanding and enabling the follow-up local inspection mission to be planned in detail. Road tunnels present a particular challenge for autonomous inspection due to the unavailability of GNSS for localization, the dark and featureless environments, the small scale of some of the faults to be detected, and the possible presence of other moving vehicles. PILOTING will produce several new technologies that address these challenges, advancing the state of the art within robotic infrastructure inspection systems.

Figure 7. “Project Overview” → “PILOTING Uses Cases”.

COOPERATION

BugWright2

The overall aim of this project is to offer robotic services on or around the hulls of commercial vessels: A large scale pilot experimental commercial service for robotic ship-outer-hull inspection and cleaning with increasing level of technological complexity. The EU-funded BugWright2 project will facilitate a multi-robot visual and acoustic inspection of the whole structure from robotic platforms in the air and underwater, detecting corrosion patches or cleaning the surface as necessary.

<https://www.bugwright2.eu/>

ATLANTIS

The overall aim of the ATLANTIS project is to establish a pioneer pilot infrastructure capable of demonstrating key enabling robotic technologies for inspection and maintenance of offshore wind farms that will be installed in the Atlantic Ocean. A large-scale pilot will be operated and demonstrated by a strong collaboration between the research community and the industrial offshore energy ecosystem.

<https://www.atlantis-h2020.eu/>

RIMA

RIMA (Robotics for Inspection and Maintenance) is a 4-year project aiming to tackle this gap by establishing a network of 13 Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) and industry associations to support the uptake of robotics – and help small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) to develop novel solutions for different industry sectors through 2 Open Call rounds (2019 / 2020) with a total amount of 8.1M€.

<https://rimanetwork.eu/>

HYFLIERS

Hybrid Flying-Rolling with Snake Arm Robot for Contact Inspection is an European project in which a hybrid robot is being developed to allow the inspection of pipe bends in the petrochemical industry. FADA-CATEC main role is the development of hybrid aerial robots able to land on pipes at industrial plants, and move along them performing inspection, and control and localization techniques.

<http://hyfliers-project.eu/>

AERIAL-CORE

AERIAL-CORE, H2020 European project, aims to the development of core technology modules and an integrated aerial cognitive robotic system that will have unprecedented capabilities on the operational range and safety in the interaction with people, or Aerial Co-Workers for applications such as the inspection and maintenance of large linear infrastructures.

<https://aerial-core.eu/>

Figure 8. “Project Overview” →”Cooperation”.

2.4 Consortium tab

This tab contains the list of PILOTING partners (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. “Consortium” tab

By clicking on each partner logo you can find a short description of each company, its relevance previous experience and its role in PILOTING project. In addition, it has been included a link to the official website of each one, where all general information about the partner and the contact details can be found (see the example for FADA-CATEC in Figure 10).

The coordinator of PILOTING project is FADA-CATEC. Andalusian Foundation for Aerospace Development (FADA) is a non-profit organization that takes care of the management of CATEC research centre. The main goal is R&D on aerospace related technologies in coordination with industries, universities and other research centres. FADA-CATEC counts with more than 20 researchers working specifically on aerial robotics technologies and it has a large experience developing solutions and application with aerial robots.

Andalusian Foundation For Aerospace Development
<http://www.catec.aero>

ROLE IN THE PROJECT AND MAIN TASKS

FADA-CATEC will be the coordinator of the project and will contribute mainly to WP1 (Ethic Requirement), WP2(Coordination) and WP7 (Iterative system integration). In addition, to contributing to other technical WPs, especially in the development of aerial-robotics related technologies and the general robot control station, FADA-CATEC will be active in WP10 in Exploitation, Communication and Dissemination.

RELEVANT PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE

FADA-CATEC has a vast experience developing aerial robots for inspection applications. and then, integrating and demonstrating the developed technologies in realistic environments and increasing the TRL of novel robotics technologies. In fact, FADA-CATEC won the Overall Innovation Radar Prize 2017 granted by the European Commission for its technology for industrial contact inspection using aerial robots (<http://www.euronews.com/2017/12/04/new-drone-technology-wins-innovation-radar-prize-2017>), being the first time a robotic technology has won this prize. Also, FADA-CATEC, along with University of Seville and Airbus D&S, was awarded the Special Innovative Prize at the 1st EU Drones Award. On the other hand, FADA-CATEC has a strong activity related to the future certification of UAS and has actively participated in the working groups that is helping in the definition of the future European regulation with EASA (European Aviation Authority), and also, is part of the Advisory Committee of AESA (Spanish National Aviation Authority) and is a member of the Informal Drone Expert Group created by the European Commission. Moreover, FADA-CATEC is also participating in the definition of future industrial standards for aerial robots. FADA-CATEC is a limited member of EUROCAE (European Organisation for Civil Aviation Equipment) and participates in WG-105 Working Group (Unmanned Aircraft Systems), leading the SORA Focus Team and participating in the FAS Ad Hoc Group on adaptation of DO-178/ED-12 to UAS (join activity between RTCA and EUROCAE). FADA-CATEC is also a member of the WG for UAS in AENOR which the Spanish representative for ISO committees. Finally, FADA-CATEC has a wide experience participating in European projects; having participated in 9 FP7 projects (coordinating 3 of them: ARCAS, EC-SAFEMOBIL and MUAC-IREN) in the last 10 years and already participating in 8 H2020 projects.

Figure 10. “Project Overview” →”FADA-CATEC” tab

2.5 News tab

The news tab of the PILOTING website gives updates on the project’s latest news with the links to more information.

Figure 11. “News” tab

2.6 Public Material tab

This tab has included a section for publications and datasets and another for multimedia content.

Publications and datasets

For publications, a Zenodo PILOTING community has been created. The section for publications and datasets include the link to this community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/piloting/>). Once a result of the project has been published or accepted it will be uploaded to the Zenodo community.

The PILOTING website “Publications and datasets” section is presented in Figure 12 below.

Multimedia

All the audiovisual content generated during the project will be uploaded in this tap. During the project will be developed multimedia content like videos presenting the main project outcomes or podcasts related to the I&M sector. In addition, a short description of each uploaded audiovisual material has been included in order to present clear information.

The PILOTING website “Multimedia” section is presented in Figure 13 below.

All the publications and public data sets are uploaded into ZENODO open-access repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/piloting/>

Figure 12. “Public material” →” Publications and datasets” tab

PROJECT VIDEOS

Meet our inspection robots: AEROCAM (episode 4)

"Meet our Inspection Robots" PILOTING youtube series episode. In this episode, Rafael Caballero, research expert from CATEC shows the AEROCAM, a novel visual inspection drone.

4th episode of the PILOTING YouTube serie...

European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance

Workshop oriented to present an overview of all active European Robotics & AI projects that apply Robotics and AI technologies to Inspection and Maintenance activities of any sector or application.

European Robotics & AI workshop applied to INSPECTION AND MAINTENANCE
JUNE 29TH 2021
CO-ORGANIZED BY
EUROPEAN ROBOTICS
PILOTING

PODCAST

Episode 8

Belen Riveiro, from the University of Vigo and Project Coordinator of SAFEWAY H2020 (<https://www.safeway-project.eu/en/>), presents a general overview of the project

Episode 7

Prof. Anibal Ollero, full professor at University of Seville and Scientific Advisor at FADA-CATEC, presents AERIAL-CORE H2020 project (<https://aerial-core.eu/>),

Episode 6

Marvin Dechene, head of Technology and responsible for drone inspections at APPLUS RVIS (<https://www.applus.com/global/en/>), talks about the benefits of using drones for inspection duties in the industry and the feedback from actual inspectors using robotic systems.

Figure 13. “Multimedia” tab

3. DOCUMENT REPOSITORY

In addition to the Project website, a document repository has been created with a private access to the partners in order to facilitate the exchange of information and coordination among them.

The selected tool is Basecamp. This server will be used to maintain current and historical versions of the files, such as source code and documentation. It will be also used to track the completeness of

high level tasks to be performed by project partners (especially the ones related to management, coordination, dissemination, communication and exploitation activities). Finally, a share calendar is also implemented to facilitate the coordination between partners.

3.1 Repository Structure

After a successful login the project member enters the project area. In the initial screen you can find the main sections of PILOTING repository. The current structure of PILOTING folder includes 4 sections (see Figure 14).

Figure 14. PILOTING repository initial screen.

3.1.1 To-dos

In this section each partner can include next actions to be completed within PILOTING project. The actions have been classified for sections: events, WPs, etc.

The PILOTING repository “To-dos” section is presented in Figure 15 below.

The screenshot displays the 'To-dos' section of the PILOTING repository. At the top, there is a '+ New list' button on the left, the 'To-dos' title with a progress indicator '4/37' in the center, and a 'View as...' dropdown on the right. Below this header, there are six task cards arranged in a 2x3 grid. Each card represents a different work package (WP) or coordination task. Each card includes a progress indicator (e.g., '4/15 completed'), a title, a list of tasks with checkboxes, due dates, and assigned team members.

Task Card	Progress	Title	Tasks	Due Date	Assigned Members
1	4/15 completed	KOM actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Honeywell must assign a member to the Steering Committee and another one to the Industry Executiv... [Jan 31] Each partner gets at least 8 members for the PILOTING User G... 	Jan 31	Martin W.
2	0/2 completed	Administrative tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First 9 months financial information request [Oct 11, 2020] First 14 months financial information request [Mar 7, 2021] 	Oct 11, 2020; Mar 7, 2021	Antidio V., María J., Macarena M., A...
3	0/2 completed	WP1 Ethics requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D1.1 H - Requirement No. 1 [M06, R, CO] D1.2 POPD - Requirement No. 2 [M06, R, CO] 	Apr 30, 2020 - Jun 30, 2020	Antidio V., María J., Macarena M.
4	0/4 completed	WP2 Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D2.1 Project Management Handbook [M02, R, CO] D2.2 Data Management Plan [M06, R, CO] 	Jan 1, 2020 - Feb 28, 2020; Apr 30 - Jun 30	Antidio V., María J., Macarena M., Mar...
5	0/2 completed	WP3 Specification and design of PILOTING I&M Robotic-based platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D3.1 PILOTING system specifications [M06, R, CO] 	Apr 30 - Jun 30	Antidio V., Miguel Á., Francisco J., Antonio J., Juan N., C...
6	0/2 completed	WP4 Adaptation of robotic vehicles and data gathering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D4.1 PILOTING first robotic vehicles [M18, DEM, PU] 	Apr 30, 2021 - Jun 30, 2021	Antidio V., Miguel Á., Francisco J., Antonio J., Juan N., C...

Figure 15. PILOTING repository “To-dos” section

The tool allows to designate the person in charge of doing the action and the due date.

3.1.2 Docs&Files

All the information produced by the consortium or relevant to the project will be uploaded in this section. The following folders have been created:

1. A folder for public material, where any public access information will be uploaded. All the information that is not in this folder will be considered confidential.
2. A folder for Project Meetings where, at least, one folder for each project meeting held will be created. In these folders all the information related to the event will be uploaded: agenda, minutes, list of attendees, pictures, etc. In addition, a folder with useful templates (poster, attendance list, agenda, etc) for organizing PILOTING events has also been included.

3. A folder for each WP where at least a folder for each deliverable has been created. Any additional folder can be created to upload other generated documents. These can also be uploaded directly to the work package folder.

The PILOTING repository “Docs&Files” section is presented in Figure 16 below.

Figure 16. PILOTING repository “Docs&Files” section

3.1.3 Schedule

Basecamp tool allows each partner to see all the pending actions and their due date on a calendar (see Figure 17).

[+ New event](#) **Schedule**

[Add this Schedule to your Google Calendar, Outlook, or iCal...](#)

January							February						
MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN	MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
		1	2	3	4	5						1	2
6	7	8	9	10	11	12	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
27	28	29	30	31			24	25	26	27	28	29	

Wed, Jan 29 **CA must be signed by CHEVRON, HONEYWELL, EGNATIA and USE and sent to CATEC (by email and postal)** 1 RR AD GH PP MW
Completed Jan 29
KOM actions

D2.1 Project Management Handbook [M02, R, CO] MM MM
Jan 1 - Feb 28
WP2 Coordination

Thu, Jan 30 D2.1 Project Management Handbook [M02, R, CO]

D10.1 Project website [M03, R, PU] MM MM
Jan 30 - Mar 31

Figure 17. PILOTING repository “Schedule” section

3.1.4 Message board

Finally, and in addition to email lists, Basecamp will be used to announce important events in PILOTING project.

The PILOTING repository “Message board” section is presented in Figure 18 below.

[+ New message](#) **Message Board** All messages

 KOM minutes uploaded
Antidio Viguria • Jan 22 — The minutes of the KOM have been uploaded into Docs&Files->Project Meetings ->KOM_2020_01_15-16->PILOTING Minutes-Kick-Off-

 Pictures of Kick-off meeting
Announcement by Celia R. Revert • Jan 17 — Hi there everyone! I have uploaded the pictures taken during the kick-off meeting a folder called "KoM Pictures". They

Figure 18. PILOTING repository “Message board” section

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents the PILOTING project website and its main contents and structure. Also, the deliverable presents the Basecamp tool that will be used to share information within partners and facilitate their coordination.